

Levels of Social Intelligence Vis-à-Vis Interface of Social-Media Usage: An Exploratory Study

Mohd Raziq¹
Research Scholar,
Central University of Gujrat, Gandhinagar

Dr. Shiva Shukla²
Associate Professor,
Guru Kashi University, Talwandi Sabo

OrcID identifier: 0000-0002-4036-4736

Abstract:- The present study explored social media usage in the context of university students' social intelligence levels. The study involved a sample of 208 students who were further divided based on their levels of social intelligence. The data was gathered from students using social media for over five years. The findings were analyzed, and interpretations were drawn. Finally, suggestions were made based on the results.

Keywords:- Interpersonal intelligence, social-media usage, social networking sites, online learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social networking has changed the way to communicate with each other daily. The Social life of the average individual has changed in the last few decades because of online connections with friends, relatives or family. The students use social media to make connections with their friends and as well as with their family members. Social relations employing social media have become simple, easier and frequent. This can be said not only for personal communication but also the social connectivity and interface are changing in professional and academic communications. Social media is popular among the young generations and widely used by students. University students are a sizable percentage of the population using social media frequently. The social media currently plays a crucial role in the field of education (Griffin & Zinskie, 2021). This has increased more so ever post-COVID-19 scenario.

II. SOCIAL MEDIA, LEARNING AND UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

The social media and social networking sites help users befriend others, communicate and share information with a global audience, pass their free time, manage their social life, and enhance their networking skills (Madge et al., 2009). Social networking sites present teachers and the new generation of students with huge opportunities for synchronous and asynchronous learning (Jee, 2011). These social networking sites are also user-friendly and helpful in forming collaborations and exchanging ideas and information (Stanley, 2013). Social media and social networking sites can help students bond with their peers (Godwin-Jones, 2010) and reshape or redefine their relationships with their teachers.

Integrating social media and social networking sites into language learning programs reflected a positive correlation between the users and their writing skills (Al-Shehri, 2011). They also reflect a developed socio-pragmatic competence (Chen, 2013). Using social media in learning helps engage in peer feedback and assessment activities (McCarthy, 2010). It was further found that students could share or even design interactive multimedia resources themselves (Kern et al., 2008). Social media users could subscribe to a visible forum to access learning resources in different modalities. This helped them reach out to other users to discuss their learning problems or the content of a new lesson (Horwitz, 2008). The social media and social networking sites were found to help supplement a traditional classroom, and students were found to be achieving learning outcomes with their help (Naghdi-pour & Eldrige, 2016). There have been some downsides to using social media among students also. A problematic social media use has been a matter of concern for many of late. Not every user has positive outcomes. A small portion of the population reports addiction-like symptoms, become problematic users, and experienced detrimental effects from it (Hawi & Samaha, 2017).

III. SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE, SOCIAL MEDIA AND UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

A study found that university students, both men and women, had good levels of interpersonal intelligence (Sundarrajan & Gopisundaran, 2018). Individuals with high interpersonal and intrapersonal intelligence were found to experience reduced levels of social media stress (Sundvik & Davis). Intrapersonal Intelligence is one factor that predicts key learning outcomes in higher education, including the students' GPA, generic outcomes, and satisfaction with the university experience (Zohc et al., 2020).

Emotional Intelligence encompasses both intrapersonal intelligence as well as interpersonal intelligence. Individuals with lower interpersonal Intelligence experience health, psychological, and behavioural problems more frequently than those with higher interpersonal intelligence (Austin et al., 2005). The same was true about problematic social media usage also. Higher intrapersonal and inter personal intelligence predicted lesser problematic social media usage (Süral et al., 2019). In a similar study, social intelligence was found to be negatively related to internet addiction, psychological distress and peer victimisation (Hsieh et al., 2019).

IV. THE RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

After carefully reviewing the literature, it is evident that social media use can benefit academic activities in higher education. It is important to have high social intelligence to negate harmful effects like internet addiction and cyber victimization like trolling, bullying, etc. A need was felt to study the interface of social media usage following university students' social intelligence level.

V. THE POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The study population was fourth-semester postgraduate students of the Central University of Punjab Bathinda. There were 452 students enrolled as per the official record, of which 331 were in Science, and 121 were in Arts stream.

A. Sample of the Study

For the population of 452 a sample frame of 208 students with 5% margin for error and 95% confidence level was determined.

B. Sampling Techniques

The data collection was done by selecting 208 students who were further divided by using the Proportionate Stratified technique in strata of Arts and Science students, and further dividing them based on gender where each stratum is proportionate to its population size.

VI. DATA COLLECTION

The investigator, by using a proportionate stratified random sampling technique, made a sample of 208 students who were enrolled at the university for Post Graduate programs for the 4th semester and collected the data. The investigator consulted the HODs of every department and sought permission from concerned authorities. After seeking approval, the investigator interacted with students to build rapport and then instructed them about the questionnaires. The investigator, after providing adequate instruction, administered the test to them.

VII. TOOLS FOR DATA COLLECTION

A. Social Intelligence

In order to collect the data investigator used the standardized social intelligence scale developed by Chadha (1986), which had 66 multiple-choice type test items divided in eight dimensions distributed with the following scheme, a) patience, b) cooperativeness, c) confidence, d) sensitivity, e) recognition of social environment, f) tactfulness, g) sense of humour and h) memory. The subject had to select only one most appropriate answer in seven dimensions, and in the eighth dimension, had to look at photographs and recognize personalities.

B. Usage of social media

For social media usage, the investigator used a self-constructed questionnaire with 21 items with a multiple-choice questionnaire with few open-ended options scheduled to explore the association between the usage of seven types of social media. The questionnaire was based on four dimensions a) habits, b) interest, c) involvement, d) participation and e) communication. The questionnaire was analyzed item-wise utilizing percentage analysis, and the items which had open-ended options were analyzed by utilizing content analysis.

C. Technique of Analysis and Interpretation

The multiple-choice questionnaire was analyzed using percentage analysis Graphs and Pie-Charts while the items with open-ended options were analyzed using Content Analysis.

VIII. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

A. The difference between levels of social intelligence for university students

As the study was dependent on answers on social media usage questionnaire given by students with varying levels of social intelligence, namely high, medium and low. The obtained scores were analyzed using one-way ANOVA. The analyzed data results are given in table 1 with mean, standard deviation, and obtained levels of social intelligence. The sample frame was thus divided into 20 university students with high social intelligence, 165 with medium and 23 with low social intelligence.

Table 1: Levels and percentage of Social Intelligence of Students of CUPB

Variable	Total Students	Mean	SD	Level	Z-Score	N	Percentage
Social Intelligence	208	88.55	8.58	High	1.10 and above	20	9.62
				Average	-0.99 to 0.98	165	79.33
				Low	-1.11 and below	23	11.05

Fig. 1: Pie-chart for Percentage of levels of Social Intelligence of university students

B. The hours in a day spent by students on social media

Students with low, average and high social intelligence reported spending 3-5 hours on their social media accounts daily, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Comparative bar diagram for time spent on social media by students

C. Frequency in a day for checking social-media accounts by students

Students with low, average and high social intelligence reported to mostly have a frequency of regular interval for

checking their social-media account throughout the day as in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Comparative bar diagram for habit of checking social media by students

D. Number of social-media accounts of students

Students with low, average and high social intelligence reported mostly to have 2-5 activesocial-media accounts as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: Comparative bar diagram for number of social media accounts of students

E. Primary reason for using social media by students

Students with low social intelligence reported mostly using social media for academic purposes and sharing equally; average social intelligence students reported mostly

using social media for networking and high social intelligence students reported mostly using social media for academic purposes, as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: Comparative bar diagram for the primary reason for using social media by students

F. Accessing of social media by students

Students with low, average and high social intelligence reported mostly to be using social media during free time as displayed in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: Comparative bar diagram for social media access by students

G. Using social media for educational purposes by students
 Students with low, average and high social intelligence reported mostly checking their social media accounts for

educational purposes any time of the day, as shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7: Comparative bar diagram for using social media for educational purposes

H. Social media platform used most by students
 Students with low, average and high social intelligence mostly reported WhatsApp as their preferred social media

platform, followed by Facebook and YouTube, as shown in figure 8.

Fig. 8: Comparative bar diagram for social media platform used most by students

I. Most interesting aspect of using social media for students
 Students with average and high social intelligence reported mostly to find learning new things to be the most interesting aspect of social media, while students with low

social intelligence reported finding instant messaging and learning new things equally to be the most interesting aspect of social media, as displayed in Figure 9.

Fig. 9: Comparative bar diagram for the most interesting aspect of using social media

J. Preference for using social media by students

Students with low, average and high Social Intelligence reported mostly prefer using social media for academic purposes, as given in Figure 10.

Fig. 10: Comparative bar diagram for preference for using social media by university students

K. Communication platforms used by students while sharing News

Students with high social intelligence reported mostly to be preferred instant messaging for communicating news

while students with average and low Social Intelligence reported to mostly prefer voice call to communicate news as shown in Figure 11.

Fig. 11: Comparative bar diagram for communication used by students while sharing news

IX. CONTENT ANALYSIS

The multiple-choice questionnaire had a few open-ended options. While most participants chose to select from the given choices, a few opted to answer the open-ended possibilities. Their responses are discussed as follows.

- Students with high social intelligence reported the news, current affairs and updates as the primary reason for using social media.
- Students with average social intelligence reported their primary reason for using social media as to know daily verses (quotations), to stay in touch with friends and know what they are doing, to find products to buy and to update news and current affairs.
- Students with low social intelligence informed the primary reason for using social media for news updates.
- Students with average social intelligence reported accessing social media: before sleeping, while in gym
- Students with average social intelligence reported the most interesting aspect of using social media to keep in touch.

- Students with average social intelligence conveyed preference for using social media mostly for: video shooting, news, technological advances and personal interest videos.

X. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the research question have drawn conclusions for qualitative data. The conclusions are described as follows:

- It was found that in all three levels (low, average and high) of social intelligence, students using social media for more than five years, spent 3-5 hours on social media daily, had 2-5 social media accounts, WhatsApp to be their preferred social media platform, using social media for academic purpose and communicating with their friends.
- Students with low social intelligence reported mostly using social media for academic purposes and sharing equally; average social intelligence students said they mostly used social media for networking and high social

- intelligence students reported mostly using social media for academic purposes.
- Students with average and high social intelligence reported mostly to find learning new thing to be most interesting aspect of social media while students with low social intelligence reported to mostly find instant messaging and learning new things equally to be most interesting aspect of social media.
 - Students with high social intelligence reported news, current affairs and updates as primary reason for using social media.
 - Students with average social intelligence reported their primary reason of using social media as: to know daily verses (quotations), to stay in touch with friends and what they are doing, to find products to buy and to up- date news and current affairs.
 - Students with low social intelligence informed primary reason for using social media for news update.
 - Students with average social intelligence reported the most interesting aspect of using social media to keep in touch with friends and family.
 - Students with average social intelligence conveyed preference for using social media mostly for: video shooting, news, technological advances and personal interest videos.

XI. RECOMMENDATIONS

- As the mean score of university students showed a performance of average social intelligence for the group it is recommended that university should include expert guidance and counselling on meaningful socializing of the university students.
- As the usage of social media is average by the students the university can adopt methods to include guidance of healthy social media practices for academic purposes as they would prove to be beneficial.
- Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that the University management should develop policies that encourage innovative usage of social media for educational purposes, such as group discussions, group research projects, etc., whilst minimizing its negative impact on students by controlling social media use among students during learning sessions.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Al-Shehri, S. (2011). Connectivism: A new pathway for theorising and promoting mobile language learning. *International Journal of Innovation and Leadership on the Teaching of Humanities*, 1(2), 10–31. Return to ref 2011 in article
- [2.] Austin, E. J., Saklofske, D. H., & Egan, V. (2005). Personality, well-being and health correlates of trait emotional intelligence. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 38(3), 547–558.
- [3.] Chen, H. I. (2013). Identity practices of multilingual writers in social networking spaces. *Language Learning & Technology*, 17(2), 143–170.
- [4.] Godwin-Jones, R. (2010). Emerging technologies: literacies and technologies revisited. *Language Learning & Technology*, 14(3), 2–9.
- [5.] Griffin, M. M., & Zinskie, C. D. (Eds.). (2021). *Social media: Influences on education*. Information Age Publishing.
- [6.] Hawi, N. S., & Samaha, M. (2017). The relations among social media addiction, self-esteem, and life satisfaction in university students. *Social Science Computer Review*, 35(5), 576–586.
- [7.] Horwitz, E. K. (2008). *Becoming a language teacher: A practical guide to second language learning and teaching*. Boston: Pearson Education, Inc.
- [8.] Hsieh, YP., Wei, HS., Hwa, HL. et al. The Effects of Peer Victimization on Children's Internet Addiction and Psychological Distress: The Moderating Roles of Emotional and Social Intelligence. *J Child Fam Stud* 28, 2487–2498 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10826-018-1120-6>
- [9.] Jee, J. M. (2011). Web 2.0 technology meets mobile assisted language learning. *The IALLT Journal*, 41(1), 161–175.
- [10.] Kern, R., Ware, P., & Warschauer, M. (2008). Network-based language teaching. In N. V. Deussen-Scholl & N. H. Hornberger (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of language and education (Second and foreign language education 2nd ed., pp. 281–292)*. New York: Springer.
- [11.] Madge, C., Meek, J., Wellens, J., & Hooley, T. (2009). Facebook, social integration and informal learning at university: it is more for socializing and talking to friends about work than for actually doing work. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 34(2), 141–155.
- [12.] McCarthy, J. (2010). Blended learning environments: using social networking sites to enhance the first year experience. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 26(6), 729–740.
- [13.] Naghdipour, B., Eldridge, N.H. Incorporating Social Networking Sites into Traditional Pedagogy: a Case of Facebook. *TechTrends* 60, 591–597 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11528-016-0118-4>
- [14.] Stanley, G. (2013). *Language learning with technology: Ideas for integrating technology in the classroom*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [15.] Sundararajan, S., Gopichandran, V. Emotional intelligence among medical students: a mixed methods study from Chennai, India. *BMC Med Educ* 18, 97 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-018-1213-3>
- [16.] Sundvik, L.M.S., Davis, S.K. Social media stress and mental health: A brief report on the protective role of emotional intelligence. *CurrPsychol* (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-022-03035-9>
- [17.] Süral, I., Griffiths, M.D., Kircaburun, K. et al. (2019) Trait Emotional Intelligence and Problematic Social Media Use Among Adults: The Mediating Role of Social Media Use Motives. *Int J Ment Health Addiction* 17, 336–345. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11469-018-0022-6>
- [18.] Zhoc, K.C.H., King, R.B., Chung, T.S.H. et al. Emotionally intelligent students are more engaged and successful: examining the role of emotional intelligence in higher education. *Eur J PsycholEduc* 35, 839–863 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-019-00458-0>